

Educational Development in Hyderabad State during the Nizam Period (1724–1948)

Ankam Jayaprakash

Assistant Professor of History,
Government Degree College, Yellareddy, Kamareddy Dist, Telangana
Email: ankamjayaprakash@gmail.com
Mobile No: 9948858251

ABSTRACT

The decline of the Mughal Empire in India brought many changes. Circars and Ceded districts experienced numerous vicissitudes in several areas, including administration, revenue, education, and social programmes, while being governed by the British as part of Madras Presidency. These changes, though, did not occur in the state of Hyderabad. The entire state was divided into 17 districts. Education backwardness of a given region is not isolated factor by itself but is an outcome of the historical processes. The contributions of famous people to promoting education are wonderful and will be remembered forever. Bilgarmi took the initiative to establish three industrial schools in Hyderabad, Aurangabad, and Warangal, as well as the State Central Library in Hyderabad. Raja Bahadur Venkat Ram Reddy was instrumental in establishing Narayanguda Girls' High School (renamed Madapati Hanumantha Rao School) in 1928.. Bhagya Reddy Varma not only fought for establishing schools for the children of the most marginalized sections but also established a few schools for Dalit children in Hyderabad City. The census reported a general literacy rate of 2.6 among Hindus, Muslims, Christians, and 0.8 among Animists, whereas the English literacy rate was 0.2 among Hindus, Muslims, and 16.1 among Christians. The Nizam state accepted modern education, the language policy and lack of state commitment led to the educational backwardness of Hyderabad state during the Nizam rule compared to other princely states and British India.

Key Words: Hyderabad, Nizam rule, marginalized, Central Library, Modern Education.

Introduction:

The decline of the Mughal Empire in India brought many changes. Consequently, it paved the way for European trading companies to intervene in local politics. It was the same for Hyderabad State (Hyderabad Deccan), which lost Northern Circars as a result of the Carnatic Wars and Ceded Districts as a result of its subsidiary alliance with the British. As a result, Circars and Ceded districts experienced numerous vicissitudes in several areas, including administration, revenue, education, and social programmes, while being governed by the British as part of Madras Presidency. These changes, though, did not occur in the state of Hyderabad. The Hyderabad state was divided into four divisions, namely Medak-Gulshanabad, Warangal, Aurangabad, and Gulbarga, according to the Census of the H E H the Nizam's Dominions of 1901. The entire state was divided into 17 districts. Education backwardness of a given region is not isolated factor by itself but is an outcome of the historical processes. The present study explores the historical background of the state initiative in the field of education during the Asaf Jahi period when the basic structure of the state was feudal in nature.¹

Education during Asaf Jahi Period

Urdu has been the language of instruction across the Nizam domains ever since the advent of modern education. Other than English, which was taught as a second language, only Persian and Arabic were encouraged. The government oversees all primary and secondary educational institutions. Private businesses in education were practically outlawed. Literary pursuits were considered political because they were in the public eye. Even political events need permission to be held, let alone social, cultural, or other events. The progress of education in Hyderabad state prior to 1850 was very slow. A Madarsa was started at the Juma Masjid in Hyderabad city in 1830. Later on, in 1859, the State of Hyderabad decided to open two schools in every taluk and three schools in every district. Persian and vernacular schools were opened in taluks, whereas Persian, English, and vernacular schools were opened at district headquarters. Taluk and district schools had monthly fees of one anna (6.25 paise) and two annas, respectively. However, the children who belong to the agricultural class were exempt from paying fees. The early Nizams gave importance to learning through Persian and Arabic and had no agenda for educating the masses through promotions of scholarship and learning never was overlooked. Nizam ul Mulk the first Nizam, for example replicated the

Mughal tradition and practices in his court at Aurangabad, the capital before the son Nizam Ali-II to shifted it to Hyderabad in 1762.² One distinguishing feature of the early Asaj Jahi was the shift from Persian and Arabic to Urdu. Nizam Ali's successive Prime Ministers Arastu Jha, Chandulal and Mir Alam also were liberal patrons of Urdu poets. Mahalaja Bai Chanda was a great poet, an accomplished dancer and patron of many writers of her time. She is considered as the first Urdu poetess in Hyderabad to have a Diwani (Anthology of poems) to her credit.³

New Education Institutions – Initiatives under Salar Jung –I (1853-1883)

There was a perceptible change in the attitude of the government towards education in the state after Salar Jung was appointed as Diwan in 1853, during the reign of Nasir Ud Daula. From a state of hardly any policy on education Salar Jung turned to initiatives to improve literacy levels of the people. In establishing schools and colleges and in supporting medical and engineering schools, Salar Jung's concern was the need for officials to run the government. In order to train personnel to run the administration of the state, he felt educational reforms were imperative.⁴ Salar Jung established Darul Uloom, Oriental College in 1854 with Arabic and Persian as mediums of instruction where students studied Islamic theology, law and Literature and were trained to become Maulvies and Munshis. There was also the provision for teaching languages like Urdu Telugu Marathi Kannada besides English.⁵

The students were provided with scholarships and were also assured to government service once they completed their courses.⁶ Later for effective functioning Darul Uloom was divided into separate constituent schools to teach Persian, Arabic, the Vernacular languages, English as well as Quran.⁷ In 1878 Salar Jung set up a school known as Madarsa-i-Aliya for the education of his sons and also sons of other nobles in the City. Students of this school were encouraged by the way of foreign scholarships for higher education. They were also assured of employment in government service on completion of their study.⁸

Salar Jung's nephew Mukarram-ud-Daula, set up the Madarsa-i-Aizza in 1878 exclusive for the upper classes in the city.⁹ In 1887 the intermediate classes of the chadarghat High School were merged with Madarsa-i-Aliya.¹⁰ By 1884 there were all together 162 schools in Diwani (Directly Administered) territory of the Nizam of which 13 were in Hyderabad of the total schools, 105 were the Persian schools, 35 Marathi, 19 Telugu and 3 English. Salar Jung

also appointed Divisional Inspectors for the first time to oversee the functioning and improve the quality of education provided in those Schools.¹¹ There arose at this junction the need for teacher training schools as there was dearth of qualified teachers. Therefore separate training schools called Normal school, was set up in 1860 to train teachers.¹²

Role of East India Company and Missionaries in promoting education

There are indigenous schools in the state where the emphasis is on reading, writing, and mathematics. The village's size and the parents' significance of education determine the teacher's pay in kind, which varies. The British Residency was created in Secunderabad and Christianity expanded to a small portion of Hyderabad state thanks to the Nizam's continued cordial connections with the English East India Company. The Church of England established St. George's Grammar School in Hyderabad, India, in 1834 as the city's first public school teaching in the English language. The school was established in 1834, named Hyderabad Residency School, to cater for the educational needs of the children of the British community serving the government in Hyderabad.¹³ It is the oldest English-medium school in the city and one of the oldest in India. In 1867, the school changed its name to The Chaderghat Protestant School, and in 1891, to St. George's Grammar School. In 1865, a separate girls' school was established, the first in Hyderabad¹⁴.

The Resident later established a medical school in Bolarum in 1839. The All Saints School was established in Hyderabad by the Roman Catholic Mission in 1855 to train teachers for secondary schools. The school was initially established to provide education for the children of Nizam's Army officers; however, it gradually welcomed students from all castes.¹⁵ In English-medium schools in Hyderabad City, Aurangabad, Warangal, and Gulbarga, missionaries were established. General, technical, and professional schools are among them. Due to the hiring of non-mulkis (non-locals) from Aligarh, Madras, Bombay, Bengal, etc. in administration, particularly under Salar Jung-I, Western education acquired importance. Missionaries also started orphanages, one in Hyderabad (1865) and another in Warangal (1881).¹⁶ The Victoria Memorial orphanage founded by the state government in Hyderabad in 1995 in memory of Queen Victoria, provided training to boys and girls in different occupational and skills so that they could earn their livelihood when they left the orphanage.¹⁷ W H Wilkinson, a British educationalist, who was appointed as the Secretary of

Education and also the first Director of Public Instruction (DPI) in 1869, improved the working of primary schools in the state¹⁸. His successor Maulvi Inayatul-Ur- Rahman introduced new curricula with a view to raise the standard of teaching.¹⁹

In 1872, the English School was converted into Chaderghat Anglo Vernacular School. Later it became the nucleus of the Hyderabad College, which in 1884, got affiliated to the University of Madras.²⁰

Religious Education: A demand from the community

The Madrassa-i-Deeniya was started in 1882 to impart religious training to Muslim youth. A Sanskrit school called the Vedic Dharma Prakashika started at Hyderabad in 1894 to impart religious training to Hindu boys. Another Sanskrit school, which was aided by the state established at Hyderabad in 1899. Dharmwant High School and Mufeedul-Anam High School were the first two private schools that inculcated western education with English medium in the old city, which were founded by the Malwala Kayasth family and the leaders of the Khatri caste in 1880 and 1882 respectively.

Asafia High School was established in 1895 to impart both secular and moral education among Muslim children. The Vivek Vardhini Pathasala, which was the first private Marathi school founded in Hyderabad in 1901 whereas the first Telugu school was started by Ranga Rao Kaloji in Chaderghat in 1904. The Anwar Uloom High School was founded by Moulvi Muhammed Abdul Razzak in 1909.

Girl's Education in Hyderabad State

The main obstacles to the advancement of female education during the Nizam period were the refusal of Muslims to send their daughters to school, early marriages among the Hindus, and lack of qualified female teachers. The first government Zenana school was opened during the period of Nizam-VI. Girl's education in Hyderabad state did not attract the attention of the authority till about 1870. Miss Burgess of Wesley Mission, with a long experience in Madras established in Secunderabad a girl's school in 1872. However as it was appended to the church, children belonging to Christian family is alone admitted in it.²¹ Dr.Aghornath Chattopadhyay, father of Sarojini Naidu, established in 1881, the Anglo Vernacular girls school, also known as Gloria school, for the benefit of both Hindu and

Muslim girls. Aghoranath was thus called a pioneer in promoting girls education in Hyderabad.²²

Syed Hussain Bilgrami, familiarly known as imadul Mulk another ordent votery for women education founded the girl's high school in 1885.²³ Bilgram's sister Sujat Ali started a school for girls coming from the elite sections in Hyderabad city.²⁴ The Chadarghat School was raised to the status of the first grade college affiliated to Madras University in 1881 as Nizam College with Dr Aghoranath Chattopadhyay as its first principle.²⁵

Dr. Aghoranath Chattopadhyaya started a Hindu Anglo-vernacular school in 1877 to educate both Muslim and Hindu girls. The Wesleyan Mission started girls' schools at Secunderabad and Chaderghat in 1882. Syed Hussain Bilgrami established a school for Muslim girls in 1885 with qualified staff. Needlework, domestic science, Arabic, Persian, and English were taught to girls as part of the curriculum.

An institution for girls was opened at Bolaram during the 1880s. The Mufedul-Anam High School started a primary section for girls during the 1890s. The Nampally Girls' School was established in 1890, which was the first government middle school for girls in Hyderabad state. The Stanley Girls' School was started in 1895. Later on, it upgraded as a High School in 1908 and four girls appeared for the school-leaving examination in 1911. The Telugu Normal School and Elizabeth Stanley Girls' High School, which are located in Hyderabad imparted training to Telugu teachers. The state granted stipends to the students and appointed bullock carts for their conveyance to and from the school.

Educational Reforms under Mir Osman Ali Khan

In the reigning tenure of Mir Osman Ali Khan, certain educational reforms were introduced, which were considered the most memorable achievements under his rule and had the most lasting and impressive contribution. He was the founder of the Osmania University in Hyderabad, which marked a new era in the annals of British educational policy in India. As per the census of 1911 the proportion of literacy rate per one thousand persons in the state was mere 28 which compare very unfavaroubly with the figures of few other regions of the country. For example, in Bombay Presidency, it was 70, Madras-70, Baroda-101, Mysore-63, and Hyderabad-28.²⁶ The concept of compulsory primary education was first introduced by Mir Osman Ali Khan, the seventh Nizam in the princely state of Hyderabad. In several

districts, compulsory education was implemented strictly, and children from the age of 5 to 14 years had to study at the state schools. The seventh Nizam had allocated large amounts of funds for primary education.²⁷

The idea to have a university in Hyderabad dates back to 1879, when Maulvi Jamaluddin, a professor at Ul Azhar University in Cairo, came to Hyderabad as a visitor. An Afghan by birth, the molvi was very vocal in his anti-British views and never hesitated to ventilate them even in the presence of his British compatriots. As a result, he was deported from Egypt and thus arrived in Hyderabad.²⁸ Wilfred S. Blunt a great admirer of Islamic culture, tradition, art, and literature. It was Blunt who suggested the idea of establishing a University to the Nizam, whom he considered "the most powerful Mohammedan Prince now reigning in India."²⁹ He even floated its name as Deccan University. As a result, Nizam Ali Khan, who by then had succeeded his father, Mir Mahaboob Ali Khan (1911), was convinced over the need for a University in Hyderabad. In his Farman, issued on April 26, 1917, for the establishment of the new University, the Nizam declared that Urdu to be the medium of instruction.

On the initiative of Sir Akbar Hydari, the Prime Minister, the state established a few colleges, mainly to serve as feeder institutions for the new university. The city college opened in 1921, followed by the Nampally intermediate college for girls the following year, as well as two teacher training colleges, an engineering college, and an intermediate college in Warangal between 1929 and 1931. Between 1911 and 1922, there was a significant increase in the number of schools in the state. In 1927, a private college called Jagirdar's College was established by the Jagirdars Association on the model of an English public school to provide education exclusively for the children of the Jagirdar. After the integration of the state and the abolishment of Jagirs, it was named "Hyderabad Public School" (HPS)

Language Issue in Education

The Nizam government made compulsory proficiency in Persian or Urdu for Hindu students to go to England for higher studies. In this way, the Hindus of the Hyderabad State faced cultural humiliations and political inequality. Hence, the Arya Samaj was established in Hyderabad in 1892 to protect the rights of the Hindus. The state promoted Urdu as the official language in administration by neglecting other languages such as Telugu, Marathi,

and Kannada that were spoken by the majority of people (approximately 86 percent) in Hyderabad state. Besides, the Nizam directed that state-aided education be given only in Urdu or English. Even the primary objective of Osmania University was to provide higher education for only Muslim students. Moreover, the government did not allow private institutions to impart education in the language of the people.

Several activists worked through organizations for the promotion of Telugu in the Telangana region during the Nizam rule. Kommaraju Lakshmana Rao established Sri Krishnadevaraya Andhra Basha Nilayam in Hyderabad in 1901. Two Telugu libraries, namely Sri Rajaraja Andhra Basha Nilayam' and Andhra Samvardhini Grandhalayam, were established in 1904 and 1905 at Hanumakonda and Secunderabad, respectively. The Arya Samaj played a vital role in establishing Vivek Vardini Pathasala to impart education in Marathi and English. Subsequently, the Vignana Chandrika Grandha Mandali in Hyderabad published popular literature in Telugu.

Conculution

The contributions of famous people to promoting education are wonderful and will be remembered forever. Bilgarmi took the initiative to establish three industrial schools in Hyderabad, Aurangabad, and Warangal, as well as the State Central Library in Hyderabad. Raja Bahadur Venkat Ram Reddy was instrumental in establishing Narayanguda Girls' High School (renamed Madapati Hanumantha Rao School) in 1928 and separate hostels for boys and girls belonging to the Reddy community in 1918 and 1933, respectively. Bhagya Reddy Varma not only fought for establishing schools for the children of the most marginalized sections but also established a few schools for Dalit children in Hyderabad City.

According to the Census of the H E H the Nizam's Dominions (1921), the general and English literacy rates of Hyderabad State were only 3.3 and 0.3, respectively. If we compare with other provinces and states, it stands last both in general education and in literacy in English. The census reported a general literacy rate of 2.6 among Hindus, Muslims, Christians, and 0.8 among Animists, whereas the English literacy rate was 0.2 among Hindus, Muslims, and 16.1 among Christians. The total literacy rate in the Telangana region is 4.2, whereas the total literacy rate in the Marathwada region is 2.4. Though the Nizam state accepted modern education, the language policy and lack of state commitment

led to the educational backwardness of Hyderabad state during the Nizam rule compared to other princely states and British India.

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